
THE IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZING FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS TO THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: Investment activity arises and is carried out in connection with the allocation of investment funds to the object by its subjects. The object of investment is understood to be the object that mobilizes funds, that is, all assets within the framework of the law. They can be new enterprises or already operating enterprises, securities, bank deposits, intellectual property.

Keywords: enterprises, securities, bank deposits, intellectual property.

Introduction

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investment Activity" defines the objects of investment activity as follows: "Objects of production of tangible and intangible goods are objects of investment activity"¹.

The subject of investment is understood to be legal entities and individuals carrying out investment activities. They can be: foreign states, international financial institutions, local government bodies, state management bodies, enterprises and organizations of various forms of ownership, citizens who are property owners, including foreign citizens, stateless persons.

Investment activity is associated with the sectors chosen by the investor, as well as the purposes for which investments should be spent, that is, investment objects.

Depending on the areas of investment orientation, participation in production and expenditure, the following objects of investment activity can be distinguished:

- newly created and modernized (updated) fixed assets and working capital in all sectors of the national economy;
- scientific and technical products, research, education, training and retraining of personnel;
- intellectual property, copyright, invention, discovery rights, experience;
- securities, target funds;
- other property objects;
- property rights.

When organizing investment activities, each property owner must operate with a deep understanding of the essence of business and entrepreneurship. A property owner engaged in investment activities must be able to comprehensively understand the rapidly changing market economy and its multifaceted relationships. In conducting investment activities, it is of particular importance to have marketing knowledge on the scale of the entire economy and the country, an area that relies on economic information. Because in an unstable economy, an investor without a deep understanding of the essence of money circulation, financial credit and banks, and tax policy, organizing investment activities is associated with risk and may encounter a crisis in the short term. In a mature society with developed market relations, investment activities are carried out in the following areas:

- by citizens, non-state enterprises, economic associations, collective and cooperative farms, as well as organizations established on the basis of collective ownership, non-state enterprises and institutions;

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investment Activities"

- by administrative and management units, organizations of the state and state enterprises and institutions;

- by foreign citizens, private firms, associations, companies and legal entities, as well as other foreign states and international financial and credit institutions;

The development of various forms of ownership, the establishment of entrepreneurship and business, the development of world economic relations, the increase in the role of joint ventures in stabilizing the economy create the necessary opportunities for the full organization of investment activity.

The emergence of various forms of ownership, the development of entrepreneurship, and the inflow of foreign capital also determine the directions of investment activity.

It is possible to create a category of investment activity objects based on the areas of investment attraction and expenditure. The category of investment activity objects based on the areas of investment expenditure is shown in the figure below.

Figure 1. Classification of investment activity objects²

The state uses various measures to develop investment activities. It should be noted that significant achievements have been made in this regard in world practice. Given that the establishment and development of free economic zones occupies a special place among them, it is possible to have a clear and detailed conclusion about the importance of such zones and the relevance of studying the foundations of their organization.

Literature Review

Literature review (analysis) on the topic of the article. Leading world economists on the problems of organizing free economic zones: Basile A., Germedis D., Simadzaki T., Isikhori S., Rotbrand M., Saydlovska - Martini E., Danko T., Okrut Z., Gitman L., Dzhonk M., Tatsuno SH, Xuy Szoshe, Say Jenshun and others conducted research and comprehensively studied this problem in their scientific works. Leading economists from the CIS countries: Avdokushin E.F., Faminsky I.P., Ovchinnikova S. G., Voynov I.O., Zamyatin B.I., Druzik S., Zimenkov R.I., Ignatov V. G., Komlev Yu., Leussy A., Kuznitsov Yu. I., Guo Zhenga, Elisa Barbieribc, Marco R.Di Tommaso Sergey Sosnovskikh , Lychagin A.I. , and others studied the organization of free economic zones and their integration in their scientific works.

² Nazarova et al. World economy and international economic relations. Textbook. T.: TSUE, "Economics"

Among the economists from Uzbekistan: Tokhliev N., Takeanov A., Zheng V.A., Kholikulov A.R., Shermukhammedov A., Nizamov A.B., Khamroev X.R., D.Gozibekov, N.Karimov, N.Khaydarov, E.Nosirov, Q.Khoshimov, D.Khojamkulov, Sh.Akhmadjonov, M. Raimzhanova, Oblamurodov N.N., Rustamov D.D., Karimov N.G', Vahabov A.V., Hojibakiev Sh.Kh., Mominov N.G', Oblamurodov N.N. and others, in their scientific works, have studied the theoretical and methodological foundations of the organization of free economic zones in our country.

Discussion

The importance of the establishment of free economic zones in the development of investment activities and improving the attraction of investments to the economy can be expressed in the following:

1. It has a positive impact on the development of investment activities in the country.
2. It allows for the attraction of a wide range of domestic and foreign investments to the country's economy and the development of the activities of economic entities of various forms of ownership.
3. It ensures the acceleration of the integration of the national economy into the international economy.
4. It affects the increase in the scale and quality of national production, services and work.
5. It affects the increase in employment and intellectual potential of the population.
6. It allows for an increase in national income and an increase in domestic financial and foreign exchange reserves.
7. It affects the competitiveness of the national economy.
8. It affects the investment attractiveness of the national economy.
9. It affects the development of new aspects of entrepreneurial activity based on free competition.
10. It affects the further increase in the number of international partners of the country, etc.

The EIH has a strong impact not only on its territory, but also beyond its territory, on the entire national economy. This impact is mainly of a modernization nature and is carried out through a number of channels and mechanisms. One of these impacts is the visibility of a particular territory at the national level. With their novelty, such territories and the first foreign firms established in them attract the attention of national entrepreneurs.

The importance of Free Economic Zones in the modern economy is also evident from their spread across the world. Currently, Free Economic Zones exist in all continents and regions of the world. All countries that are facing economic development are trying to use the mechanism of Free Economic Zones, which is a great tool of liberalization, to accelerate their development. The following table is proof of this idea.

Table 1

Distribution of free economic zones by country in the world³

World regions	Number of countries in the region	Countries with EITs*	Percentage	Countries without EIBs**	Percentage
Developed countries	32	28	87,5	4	12,5
Latin America	45	41	91,1	4	8,9
Africa	54	13	24,1	41	75,9
Asia	37	26	70,3	11	29,7
Oceania	18	11	61,1	7	38,9

³ The World Bank "Global Financial Development Report 2015", 2016 year page- 32-33

Economic transition countries	32	24	75,0	8	25,0
Total	218	143	65,6	75	34,4

Note: * countries that currently have IEDs or have used them in the past decades.

** countries that do not have IEDs or have no clear information.

The table shows that 65.6 percent of the world's countries, that is, 143 out of 218 countries, have Free Economic Zones. In order to analyze the distribution of Free Economic Zones around the world, we roughly divided the world's countries into six regions. We determined which of these regions have Free Economic Zones or not. The share of countries with Free Economic Zones is highest in Latin America and developed countries (91.1 and 87.5 percent, respectively). This institution has also been rapidly gaining ground in countries with economies in transition in recent years. In Africa, it is the least, that is, 24.1 percent.

As a result, the new methods of production management, organization, and export development used in the region have the effect of somehow learning outside the region. This effect is not immediately noticeable. However, over time, its results become more obvious and so on. Another learning channel is the presence of local firms in the region itself. Organizational proximity to foreign firms leads to the creation of important inter-firm relationships and the inevitable convergence of the management and technological levels of local and foreign firms. The third learning channel is the process of inter-firm migration of technical specialists, managers, and workers. In quantitative terms, this migration may not be very large, but in qualitative terms it can be quite significant. When an employee who previously worked in an advanced enterprise in the region, working with modern management, production organization, equipment, and technology, goes to work outside the region, he can have a positive impact on improving production indicators.

There are currently more than 11,000 free economic zones (FEZs) operating in the world, which are similar to each other, but have different names. In the context of the development of the modern world economy, as a result of the growth in the number of FEZs in countries, their export potential and the number of jobs created are also increasing. This leads to an increase in foreign exchange earnings and employment rates in countries. In conclusion, FEZs are quite widespread in the world. Free Economic Zones are especially widespread in the developed countries of Europe and North America, as well as in the countries of Southeast Asia and Latin America. In other regions, the distribution of FEZs is also very high, only on the African continent, a continent that has just recovered from colonialism and where attention to freedom has not yet risen to a sufficient level, we see less attention paid to FEZs. This leads to the conclusion that it is appropriate to use this tool, which is widespread in the world, to accelerate economic growth in Uzbekistan.

The organizational and legal system of free economic zones is diverse. In some cases, it is difficult to accurately classify a particular free economic zone, since they have the characteristics of many regions. Russian experts have developed a classification based on economic specialization - the specialization of the majority of firms operating in the region. The central place in the classification of free economic zones is given to industrial processing zones.

Two conceptual approaches are used in the organization of free economic zones: territorial and functional (point). In the first case, all resident enterprises in the zone enjoy privileges in their economic activities. According to the second approach, a firm can use a preferential regime applicable to certain types of entrepreneurial activity, regardless of the region of the country in which it is located.

Examples of the first approach include free economic zones in China, the Manaus region (Brazil), and export-processing zones in developing countries. The result of the second approach can be offshore companies, duty-free shops.

One of the simplest forms of free economic zones is free customs (duty-free) zones. These zones, like free trade zones, are part of the first generation of zones. In these zones, transit or consignment warehouses, packaging of goods intended for export and minor processing are located. Such zones are often called bond warehouses or free customs zones. Free customs zones are exempt from customs duties on the import and export of goods. They exist in many countries.

Free trade zones are also widespread in the world. Free trade zones are most developed in the United States. Their organization was provided for by a special law in 1934. Its purpose is to stimulate trade, speed up trade operations, and reduce trade costs.

Table 2

Types of free economic zones ⁴

№	Trade-oriented	Industrial production oriented	Focused on technical areas	Service-oriented
1.	Free customs	Import-substituting	Technopolis	Offshore
2.	Bond warehouses	Export production	Technopark	Financial centers
3.	Free port	Industrial parks	Areas developing new and high technologies	Banking services
4.	Free trade zone	Maquiladoras	Focused on technical areas	Tourist services Ecopark

Such zones are limited areas in the United States, within which the general economic regime, including foreign economic activity, is established. The law stipulates that at least one free foreign trade zone may be established at each official port.

In accordance with US legislation, free trade zones in the country are divided into general and special (sub-zone) zones. General zones are located in a small area (several square kilometers) and are outside the national customs territory. They are used for warehousing and processing of imported goods (packaging, sorting, etc.).

The activities of sub-zones are organized for individual large companies that go beyond the general zone. In the sub-zones, goods are produced for export or import-substituting. By the mid-1990s, there were about 500 free trade zones in the United States.

Special duty-free shops at large international airports can be added to the list of ordinary free trade zones. From the regime point of view, they are considered outside the borders of the state. Free trade zones can include traditional free ports with a preferential status.

Industrial production zones are considered second-generation zones. They arose as a result of the evolution of free trade zones, as not only goods but also capital are imported into free trade zones, and not only trade, but also production activities are carried out there.

Industrial production zones are organized in territories with a special customs regime. They produce goods for export or import substitution. These territories receive significant tax and financial benefits. Export production zones are especially widespread in developing countries. The modern model of such zones is based on the territorial system established at Shannon Airport in Ireland in 1959. The greatest effect of such zones was obtained in “newly industrialized countries”.

The logic of organizing export production zones was determined by the economies of developing countries. In the mid-1960s, there was a need to stimulate industrial exports and increase employment levels with the help of foreign capital inflows.

Technology transfer zones are considered third-generation zones (1970s-1980s). They are formed spontaneously or are specially organized with state support around large scientific centers. They concentrate national and foreign research, design, and scientific and production companies using a single tax and financial system.

The largest technology transfer zones operate in the USA, Japan, and China. In the USA, they are called technoparks, in Japan, technopolises, and in China, they are called areas of new and advanced technologies.

The most famous and largest technopark in the world, Silicon Valley, accounts for 20% of the world's production of computing equipment and computers. In total, there are more than 80 such

⁴ The table was compiled by the author based on a study of economic literature.

zones in the USA. In Japan, about twenty technopolises have been created on the basis of advanced scientific organizations within the framework of special government programs. Even in the 20th century, such zones were usually established during the implementation of state plans for the development of science and technology. In the mid-90s, more than 50 new and advanced technology development zones were operating in China.

Areas where preferential conditions for entrepreneurial activity are created for firms and organizations providing various financial, economic, insurance and other services are called service zones.

Service zones include offshore zones (OS) and tax havens (TH). OTH and TH attract entrepreneurs with favorable currency and financial, fiscal conditions, good protection of banking and commercial secrets, and low state administration.

The similarities of free economic zones of various types are that they provide entrepreneurs with a favorable investment climate with customs, financial, tax benefits and advantages over the general regime.

Conclusion

In modern theoretical works of national and foreign authors, there is no single opinion on the definition of free economic zones and their classification. The organizational and functional structure of free economic zones is diverse. In modern practice of the world economy, there are up to 26 types of free economic zones. It is very difficult to uniformly classify one or another free economic zone, since they have the characteristic features of many regions. The most common free economic zones in the world are:

- customs zones;
- duty-free trade zones
- free customs zones;
- free trade zones;
- foreign trade zones;
- duty-free export-production zones;
- free export zones;
- free export-production zones;
- export-production zones;
- free economic zones;
- zones of economic convenience;
- zones of industrial export-oriented zones;
- entrepreneurial zones;
- joint venture zones;
- zones of technical and economic development;
- zones of new and high-tech development;
- technical-introduction zones;
- scientific-industrial parks;
- offshore centers;
- international offshore financial centers;
- free banking zones;
- ecological-economic zones;
- small industrial zones;
- tourism centers.

Despite the differences in the names and organizational-functional purpose of free economic zones, the following definition of free economic zones can be formulated based on a number of common features. Free economic zones are understood as territories (in some cases separated from the state customs border) with extended independence in solving economic issues, a special management regime and preferential conditions for the economic activity of investors. This general definition allows us to place several terms in one general row, distinguishing territories of various types and forms found in world practice.

At the same time, in order to have a complete picture of the subject under consideration, it

is necessary to supplement this definition with some descriptions. This allows us to divide the free economic zones existing in the world into several groups, that is, to categorize them.

The categorisation of free economic zones can be carried out according to the following four main criteria:

- by the nature of activity or functional purpose;
- by the degree of integration into the world and national economy;
- by industry designation;
- by form of ownership.

By the nature of activity or functional purpose, four main types of zones can be distinguished: free trade zones, export-production zones, scientific and industrial parks, offshore centers. Free trade zones include zones whose main functions are the import, storage and sorting of goods without additional processing. In some cases, insignificant processing of foreign goods for the purpose of their subsequent re-export is also allowed. Despite the savings in customs duties and costs, the opportunities for developing export production and attracting national, material and labor resources to it are quite limited. This explains why this type of free economic zones is not widely used in modern international practice.

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